

Humanization in educational environments; aspects necessary for living in school today

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While it is true, quality has always been measured through statistics and percentages, often forgetting the formation of the integral person.

Now, when we talk about issues such as humanism and technology-supported education, we can fall to extremes: it is common to label technology as the provider of all evils in today's civilization; or the opposite assumption; to argue that incorporating technologies into education would be the panacea to all the problems it faces and finally, to assume that the issue of the humanities is more typical of actions and attitudes of the past than as a current need providing vitality in any educational process. However, and fortunately for the educational community, today there are global efforts to make the educational task a human action that minimizes the inequities and the abysmal differences existing in countries like ours. Fernando Reimers says: "Equal educational opportunities must be the priority objective of educational policies, the aim of education must be to contribute to making fair societies. This requires improving the learning environments of the poor, but not only because of the paths that have begun during the last decade. This aspect pointed out by Reimers is precisely the core aspect that every educational action must contemplate, the educational policies that are implemented in our country must guarantee, above all, the construction of a fair and egalitarian society, strengthening the cultural wealth that we have, with respect to the diversity of the people, their past, their present and especially their future.

In the discussion table of the educational institutions of the country, the design and implementation of educational programs that address the multicultural needs that exist must be a priority, to reduce the lags, reduce illiteracy and school failure, dropping out of classrooms, projects truncated, seek an education for all children and young people in the country and the incorporation of adults, with specific programs not alienating or transculturized. While it is true it is important to resume the successful experiences that other societies have had in education projects for all and for a lifetime, our project requires substantive actions, with precise objectives, with a global vision and a national mission.

I. EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY

In Chile, the government, schools and universities of the present are now concerned with designing the appropriate and relevant educational future, which allows them to face the global social and economic demands that allow the opportunity at least to insert themselves and then try to compete in the frameworks of "globalization", there are innumerable studies and actions that the various agencies responsible for educational work currently carry out with the purpose of planning from today, the future that has already been installed in our present.

The actions, at least in the discourse, are perceived impregnated with a true spirit of planning the education of tomorrow, in a less disadvantageous situation than the current one, which allows its insertion in the world market, in this context we are talking about a task certainly humanistic that tries to at least reduce the existing gap inside the country, and abroad. This gap can be observed in different dimensions: a general gap, a regional gap, a geographical gap and a digital divide, understood as the distance that separates those who have access to information and therefore to new information technologies and communications and those who have it in a limited way or do not access them. Simply put, it is the gap between the "rich in information" and the "poor in information." The digital divide has become a primary indicator of unequal opportunities.

To reduce the digital divide, it is not enough to have access to the tools, it is necessary to create a policy and regulatory environment, institutional frameworks and human training that promotes the flow of information, innovation, and the effective use of global knowledge resources.

Este nuevo modelo de accionar educativo debe tener a los derechos educativos como su centro, debe basarse en la equidad, la dignidad humana y la justicia social y debe ser guiada para abordar las necesidades y aspiraciones de todos los grupos sociales.

If we want to be inhabitants of the global village, taking into account the educational problems we have, the challenge is to achieve an education for all and for a lifetime, I end up coined by Jacques Delors in his work: Education Encloses a Treasure, where he argues that education for all, must take into account the four pillars of knowledge: Learn to know, learn to do, learn to be and learn to serve and live there because some of our questions arise; How to achieve this coexistence if we have not been able to achieve it in our own communities? Will this coexistence be possible taking into account our differences, cultural, educational, religious, ethnic, social and economic? Has current education helped to overcome these differences? Will the educational policy of our country go in the right line to achieve this goal?

The population structure of our country is a huge cultural, ethnic, religious educational, economic and social mosaic, these enormous differences place us in alarmingly unequal and inequitable contexts, with deep and lagging senses and huge inequality of opportunities of various kinds.

It should be clarified that our cultural wealth is what defines us as a strong and powerful country, our obligation is to appropriate it, maintain it and strengthen it. The school has been until nowadays the main conductive channel towards the education and culture of the people, precisely because of this, it requires today as always and perhaps more than ever appropriate policies, extraordinary supports, national consensus, that manage to diminish that enormous heterogeneity that it divides us, which distances us that makes us ignorant, that leads to inequalities, that prevents progress, and that has delayed reaching so longed for economic and social development. To locate more closely the magnitude of the problem we live, let's analyze the following data. The statistics are generally cold, produce chills when our reality is restricted in the face.

II. THE HUMANIZATION OF EDUCATION BEFORE ICT

The new communication and information technologies offer the ideal potential to expand the spectrum of teaching and learning, crossing the traditional barriers of time and space, as well as the current boundaries of educational systems. ICTs enable an improvement in face-to-face educational processes and offer more opportunities to learn in non-formal education systems.

Exploiting these possibilities is the task that we have to perform, the challenge is how. What kind of teacher and student profiles do we need, what is the appropriate curriculum, what activities will support that curriculum, such as maintaining the motivation of the different subjects involved. Obviously we must bet on the planning task, which privileges the necessary humanization of educational processes. Mediation with permanent dialogue

becomes an indispensable attribute.

Distance education as a new modality in education will then also require the implementation of a new model, a change in the educational paradigm, where the roles for both the apprentice and the teacher have new meanings, new responsibilities, new challenges and new challenges

This new model will require a joint hierarchy of planned actions involving institutional institutions at the macro and micro levels, schools, teaching, administrative, technological and students. The responsibilities of each of the intervening subjects, is also different, there must be an effective fulfillment in the new roles that they will have to assume, the biggest challenge may have to do with promoting the necessary Dialogue, The choice of means in education, to The design of teaching materials and for tutorial support should be based on the principle of maximum interactivity.

The challenge in distance modalities is a major one, because it becomes necessary to achieve a certain relative autonomy of the students, in their learning process, and I say "certain autonomy" knowing that they will be subject to the mediation of an online program assisted by the facilitator, by the tutor. For this innovative process, it is necessary to design specific pedagogical structures, which favor interaction and interactivity and collaborative work between the actors. Shorten the distance between teacher and student, and give immediate response to the latter's requirements. For this, the use of communication technologies as teaching tools is imminent, under the premise that their effectiveness will be subject to the possibility that users access them massively.

We need to avoid that, in distal education, the spatial and geographical gap is a factor of failure because of the human need for closeness of guidance guidance support. Obviously the internal and external motivation that the student possesses and receives in their learning process is important; Although we are talking about an autonomous and self-directed process, the teacher continues to be a fundamental piece, have this category of tutor, instructor or supportive companion, or advisor, In this order of ideas, the humanization of the Pedagogical Advice is proposed as an action line , under the focus on Distance Education of maximum interactivity of the instructional process and theories of student-centered learning (humanism, constructivism and collaborative learning). Even if the teacher is a member of an educating society for the sake of technification, it is necessary to preserve that traditional ingredient of culture that we call humanistic training.

CONCLUSIONS

The government and educational institutions face important challenges today, the main route is to continue to focus on development and overcome the gaps that have widened worryingly, within the country and abroad, gaps of various kinds. Today as we must never meet, join efforts to agree on dreams and proposals that make it possible to overcome the digital divide that separates us from the globalized world. It is important to emphasize and forgive if I am repetitive, Universities and schools need to design, plan on a prospective plane the model of the university we dream of, what should be inclusive but autonomous, preserving the diversity and inclusion of peoples. Today it is an emerging task to work on educational projects, models and actions that rescue ethical values, conserve and strengthen our cultural wealth and maintain the essential component of the humanization of educational processes, regardless of the type of teaching taught.

The central theme of the debates on education in our country focuses its attention on the establishment of a New Educational Paradigm, towards the design of alternative emerging models that diminish the great lags and social inequities, so that they can incorporate, to the school to a significant percentage of the population that have not had access to it "If we want to optimize the learning process of our students, we have to apply to their design everything we know about the human being as an intelligent creature that thinks and learns" Bruer, (nineteen

ninety five). Of course it is important to highlight the importance of universal and inclusive access to the information society. In this order of ideas, the education project we need must be based on people, for meaningful learning and the social construction of knowledge. Try not to lose sight of the necessary humanization of processes, meet the individual needs of each person, their own learning rhythms, the affective need that is inherent in every human being.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1.] Bruer, John T .: Grupo Planeta (GBS), 1995.
- [2.] Castells, Manuel: INTERNET AND THE RED SOCIETY.
- [3.] Delors, Jacques: EDUCATION CLOSES A TREASURE
- [4.] Fainholc, Beatriz: INTERACTIVITY IN DISTANCE EDUCATION, Ed. Paidos; Buenos Aires, Argentina.
- [5.] Ferraté, G. Alsina, C. And Pedro F. Epilogue. INTERNET AS AN ENVIRONMENT FOR DISTANCE TEACHING. Ed. Paidos, Barcelona, Spain.
- [6.] Reimers Arias, Fernando: EDUCATION, INEQUALITY AND POLICY OPTIONS IN LATIN AMERICA IN THE 21ST CENTURY
- [7.] Silvio, José: THE VIRTUALIZATION OF THE UNIVERSITY, IESALC / UNESCO, Caracas, Venezuela